

AT3C - Recommendations to Decision-Makers
Strengthening Biodiversity 2037: Independent Review, Public
Accountability and Evidence-Based Governance

ENS5010 – Global Challenges and Sustainability

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Words: 1649

AI Acknowledgement: ChatGPT (<https://chat.openai.com>) was used at several points during this assessment. Prior to drafting, it was used to support initial brainstorming and to clarify unit concepts. Following the completion of a full draft, it was used to check alignment with the assessment rubric and to refine language, grammar, and clarity. All ideas, arguments, analysis, and written content are entirely my own. No AI-generated text has been copied into this assessment, and all AI interactions were reviewed critically before any suggestions were incorporated.

Introduction

Part C of this white paper translates the evidence gaps from Part A and the rapid review findings from Part B into two evidence-based recommendations for strengthening *Biodiversity 2037*. Part A found weaknesses in the strategy's transparency around modelling assumptions, independent review, biodiversity offset outcomes, and Monitoring, Evaluation and Reporting (MER) indicators. Part B found that formalised science-policy relationships can improve evidence use when they are independent, trusted, mandated, and connected to decision-makers (Owens, 2012; Seibicke, 2025). Accordingly, this section focuses on strengthening institutional evidence uptake and public access to biodiversity information.

The first recommendation is that DEECA establish an Independent Evidence Review Panel (IERP) by mid-2027 to review assumptions, offset performance and MER indicators. The second recommendation is that DEECA also establish a Public Biodiversity Engagement and Outcomes Dashboard by 2028 to make biodiversity outcomes more visible, accessible, and accountable. A Risk Assessment Matrix was used to assess institutional uptake risk by comparing likelihood and impact (Cascade Strategy, 2020), while a 2×2 scenario planning matrix was used to test recommendations under uncertain future conditions.

Recommendation 1: Establish an Independent Evidence Review Panel

DEECA should establish an Independent Evidence Review Panel (IERP) for *Biodiversity 2037* by mid-2027. The panel would assess the evidence underpinning policy updates, modelling assumptions, biodiversity offset performance and monitoring indicators, publishing an annual evidence statement and convening a co-design workshop between scientists, Traditional Owners, and policymakers. This is feasible because DEECA already works with scientists, policy staff, and stakeholders who could help establish the panel.

This recommendation responds to the gaps found in Part A, including limited empirical detail, assumption-driven modelling, insufficient independent peer review and weak outcome evidence for biodiversity offsets and MER indicators. These weaknesses suggest that *Biodiversity 2037* needs stronger processes for translating scientific evidence into policy decisions. An independent science-policy interface (SPI) would help address these gaps by strengthening expert scrutiny, improving evidence integration, and creating clearer accountability for how evidence informs decision-making. This is supported by Part B's

finding that evidence is more likely to be used when advisory bodies are independent, clearly mandated, institutionally supported, and connected to decision-makers (Owens, 2012; Seibicke, 2025). The IERP is therefore not simply an additional advisory layer, but a mechanism for making evidence review transparent and usable.

The UK Climate Change Committee (CCC) provides a model for this recommendation, as it shows how an independent advisory body can support accountability and evidence-informed governance (Averchenkova et al., 2021). Similarly, the IERP would function as a forum for evidence review and shared learning, facilitating discussion between scientists, policymakers, stakeholders, and Traditional Owner representatives without replacing political judgement, aligning with Wagner et al.'s (2023) finding that SPIs are most effective when they are “policy informative rather than policy prescriptive” (p. 62). This design is also consistent with adaptive management and the precautionary principle, as both emphasise decision-making under uncertainty through monitoring, learning, and preventative action (Keith et al., 2011; Kriebel et al., 2001). The annual review cycle would operationalise these principles by testing assumptions, reviewing offset and MER evidence, and updating advice as new information emerges.

Recommendation 2: Establish a Public Biodiversity Engagement and Outcomes Dashboard

DEECA should establish a Public Biodiversity Engagement and Outcomes Dashboard by 2028 to help Victorians connect with nature, understand biodiversity trends, and hold decision-makers accountable for biodiversity outcomes. This recommendation responds to *Biodiversity 2037's* goal of increasing the number of Victorians who value and actively care for nature, reflecting the strategy's view that Victorians' wellbeing depends on a healthy natural environment (DELWP, 2017).

Rather than creating a new platform, the dashboard could build on DEECA's NatureKit and Victoria's Biodiversity Atlas infrastructure which already supports biodiversity mapping, species observations, decision-making and environmental reporting (DEECA, 2024, 2026). The dashboard would extend these functions by presenting MER indicators, biodiversity offset outcomes, restoration activities, and place-based biodiversity trends through an accessible public interface, making evidence easier to interpret.

The dashboard could include citizen-science features inspired by platforms such as iNaturalist, including photo-based species observations and community monitoring contributions, while separating verified monitoring data from community submissions. By making biodiversity loss more visible, local, and participatory, these features would support *Biodiversity 2037's* public engagement goal by helping more Victorians care for nature and understand that human and ecological wellbeing are interdependent (Pocock et al., 2023). However, because Callaghan et al. (2025) caution that citizen-science data can contain bias and uncertainty, community submissions would need to be verified before being used as policy evidence, protecting the dashboard's credibility while still allowing community input to strengthen feedback between the public, scientists, and policymakers.

Risk Assessment

A key operational risk for Recommendation 1 is institutional uptake. Although the IERP may produce high-quality advice, DEECA may not meaningfully integrate this advice into *Biodiversity 2037* policy decisions. This risk concerns DEECA's internal processes for receiving, responding to and applying IERP advice in ways that influence implementation, as operational risks can stem from internal processes and affect whether organisations are able to achieve established goals (Cascade Strategy, 2020). If these processes are weak, the IERP may improve evidence transparency without strengthening biodiversity decision-making or conservation outcomes.

This risk is important because robust evidence does not automatically lead to policy uptake. Key barriers such as “availability and access to research,” “clarity/relevance/reliability of research findings,” and “timing/opportunity” impact how evidence is used (Oliver et al., 2014, p. 6). Although the IERP would improve the availability of evidence, its influence would depend on clearer response processes, accessible reporting formats, and institutional pathways for using advice. This risk also has reputational consequences, as weak uptake could reduce confidence in the panel's independence and make the IERP appear more symbolic (Owens, 2012).

A Risk Assessment Matrix was selected as the fit-for-purpose tool for this analysis because ISO 31000 frames risk assessment as a process of examining uncertainty, likelihood, and consequences to support decision-making (International Organization for Standardization [ISO], 2018; Cascade Strategy, 2020). This choice is appropriate because the issue is not

whether the IERP can produce advice, but whether DEECA acts on it. As shown in Appendix B, Table B1, institutional uptake risk was assessed as Possible × High Impact, producing a very high-risk rating where evidence statements are acknowledged but not clearly linked to MER indicators, offsets, or modelling decisions.

This emphasises that DEECA should publish a formal response to each IERP evidence statement, identifying which recommendations are accepted, partially accepted, deferred, or rejected. This would reduce symbolic uptake, strengthen accountability, and improve the likelihood that evidence review influences conservation efforts. This risk could also undermine Recommendation 2 if DEECA fails to use verified citizen-science contributions in reporting and policy feedback.

Exploring Possible Futures

A 2 × 2 scenario planning matrix was used to test how these recommendations may perform under uncertain future conditions, including shifts in institutional priorities, evidence uptake and public engagement (see Appendix C, Figure C1). This is appropriate because conservation decision-making is often “reactive” rather than “proactive”, meaning *Biodiversity 2037* requires tools that can support adaptive responses to future uncertainty (Cook et al., 2014, p. 1474). Scenario planning was therefore chosen because it uses strategic foresight to map plausible futures and identify actions that remain effective under uncertainty (Cook et al., 2014).

The scenario framework is underpinned by two predetermined elements. First, Victoria will continue to face significant biodiversity pressures, as factors such as “population growth, urban development, ... invasive species, land clearing and climate change” continue to drive biodiversity decline across Victoria (Commissioner for Environmental Sustainability Victoria, 2023, p. 68). Second, evidence, monitoring and accountability will remain central to Victorian environmental governance as the 2037 target horizon approaches. These two predetermined elements are relatively certain, while institutional response and public engagement remain less predictable.

The two key drivers are institutional uptake of evidence and public engagement with biodiversity. Both were selected because Part B found that evidence uptake is stronger when advisory bodies have clear mandates, independence, institutional support, and access to

decision-makers (Owens, 2012; Seibicke, 2025), while *Biodiversity 2037* depends on Victorians valuing and caring for nature (DELWP, 2017). The major uncertainties are whether DEECA meaningfully acts on IERP advice, and whether Victorians engage with biodiversity information and citizen-science opportunities.

As shown in Appendix C, Figure C1, four scenarios emerge:

- Evidence-Led Biodiversity Governance: high evidence uptake and high public engagement allow the IERP and dashboard to reinforce each other.
- Technocratic Improvement: high evidence uptake improves internal decision-making, but low public engagement limits community involvement.
- Engagement Without Influence: high public engagement builds community interest, but low institutional uptake limits policy learning.
- Symbolic Governance: low evidence uptake and low public engagement mean both recommendations risk becoming symbolic.

The key finding from Appendix C, Figure C1 is that both recommendations' value depends on the future scenario. Recommendation 1 is more important where institutional uptake is weak, because without DEECA acting on IERP advice, the system risks shifting toward Engagement Without Influence or Symbolic Governance. Recommendation 2 is more feasible in high-engagement futures, specifically Evidence-Led Biodiversity Governance and Engagement Without Influence. However, in Engagement Without Influence, its effectiveness is limited unless public participation is connected to policy learning. Delayed or partial DEECA responses would signal weak institutional uptake, while low dashboard use would signal weak public engagement. A biodiversity crisis or extreme weather event is a wildcard that could alter any of these four outcomes.

Conclusion

This white paper argues that *Biodiversity 2037* can only be credible if biodiversity evidence is clear, transparent, independently scrutinised, and publicly accessible. Part A showed that the strategy's evidence is weakened by unclear modelling assumptions, limited independent review, and weak outcome evidence for offsets and MER indicators. Part B showed that science-policy relationships improve evidence use when they are independent, trusted, clearly mandated and connected to decision-making. Part C therefore recommends an Independent

Evidence Review Panel and a Public Biodiversity Engagement and Outcomes Dashboard. The key takeaway is that stronger evidence governance and public accountability are essential for *Biodiversity 2037* to deliver measurable outcomes.

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Appendices

Appendix A. SMART Framework Tables

Table A1. SMART Framework for Operationalising the Evidence-Based Recommendations

SMART element	Recommendation 1: Independent Evidence Review Panel	Recommendation 2: Public Biodiversity Engagement and Outcomes Dashboard
Specific	<p>Establish an IERP led by DEECA involving biodiversity scientists, Traditional Owner representatives, MER experts, and policy staff. The panel would review modelling assumptions, offset performance, MER indicators and evidence used in policy updates.</p> <p>The goal is to strengthen independent scrutiny, evidence interpretation, and accountability with Biodiversity 2037.</p>	<p>Establish a public-facing dashboard led by DEECA, building on NatureKit, Victoria’s Biodiversity Atlas infrastructure and existing public reporting systems. The dashboard would present MER indicators, offset outcomes, restoration progress, place-based trends, and clearly labelled citizen-science contributions.</p> <p>Its goal is to help Victorians connect with nature while improving transparency and accountability.</p>
Measurable	<p>Success is measured through publication of an annual evidence statement, number of assumptions, indicator and offset outcomes reviewed, DEECA responses to panel advice, and evidence of policy updates informed by review findings.</p> <p>The key targets include the first evidence statement within 12 months of operations and at least one co-design workshop per year.</p>	<p>Success would be measured through dashboard launch, number of datasets displayed, frequency of updates, user engagement, public access metrics, visibility of offset and MER outcomes, and number of verified citizen-science contributions.</p> <p>Key targets include a pilot version of the dashboard being up and running by 2028 and annual public updates through to 2037.</p>
Achievable	<p>This is feasible because it builds on DEECA’s existing scientific, policy and stakeholder networks rather than creating a completely new system. In a constrained funding environment, the panel could begin with the highest-priority evidence gaps, modelling assumptions, biodiversity offsets, and MER indicators.</p>	<p>This is feasible because it builds on existing NatureKit and Victoria’s Biodiversity Atlas spatial data infrastructure and DEECA reporting systems. In a constrained funding environment, DEECA could launch a basic map-based reporting tool first, then add interaction and citizen-science features through staged updates.</p>
Relevant	<p>Directly addresses Part A weaknesses: limited empirical detail; assumption-driven modelling; insufficient peer review; and weak outcome evidence. It also aligns with Part B findings that independent, trusted, and mandated science-policy interfaces improve evidence use.</p>	<p>Directly supports Biodiversity 2037’s goal of increasing Victorians who value and care for nature. It also addresses Part A’s transparency and MER evidence gaps by making biodiversity outcomes more visible and publicly accountable.</p>
Time-bound	<p>Establish guidelines and membership by early 2027, commence formal operations by mid-2027, and publish the first annual evidence statement by the end of 2027.</p>	<p>Begin design and stakeholder consultation in 2027, pilot the dashboard in selected regions or datasets in 2028, and expand functionality through updates to 2037.</p>

Appendix B. Risk Assessment Matrix

Table B1. Risk Matrix for Institutional Uptake Risk - Recommendation 1: Independent Evidence Review Panel.

		Impact			
		Low Impact	Moderate Impact	High Impact	Critical Impact
Likelihood	Rare	Minimal risk: Minor delays in DEECA response to IERP, with limited effect on implementation.	Manageable: Partial uptake of IERP recommendations, but DEECA provides a clear explanation and response timeline.	Serious but unlikely: DEECA acknowledges but does not meaningfully integrate IERP advice into a major policy update.	Severe but unlikely: Major conflict between IERP advice and DEECA priorities reduces confidence in the panel's independence.
	Unlikely	Manageable: Uptake is present but occasional delays occur in DEECA's response to panel advice.	Material risk: DEECA selectively adopts IERP recommendations, with minor recommendations deferred.	High risk: Evidence statements routinely acknowledged without formal response. Advice is inconsistently linked to MER, offset, or modelling decisions.	Critical Concern: Repeated non-uptake begins to damage trust in the panel.
	Possible	Moderate impact: DEECA frequently delays responses, resulting in the reduced usefulness of annual evidence statements.	High risk: DEECA selectively adopts IERP advice, leaving some evidence weaknesses only partly addressed.	Very High risk: Evidence statements may be acknowledged without formal response or clear linkage to MER, offset, or modelling decisions, reducing the IERP to a symbolic advisory function (Oliver et al., 2014; Owens, 2012).	Severe risk: Persistent non-uptake reduces stakeholder confidence in Biodiversity 2037 governance and prompts calls for redesign.
	Likely	Significant Disruption: Response delays become common, reducing policy usefulness.	Very High impact: Partial uptake becomes normalised, limiting the panel's influence.	Severe Risk IERP advice is regularly sidelined, making the panel symbolic.	Systemic failure: Independent review function fails and requires redesign or replacement.

Note. Assessed cell (bold border) indicates the evaluated risk level for institutional uptake: Possible × High Impact. Source: ISO (2018) and Cascade Strategy (2020).

Appendix C. 2 × 2 Scenario Planning Matrix

Figure C1. Future Scenarios for Biodiversity 2037 Under Varying Evidence Uptake and Public Engagement Conditions

Note. The matrix explores how the two recommendations may perform under different future conditions. Evidence-Led Biodiversity Governance is the strongest future because institutional evidence uptake and public engagement reinforce each other.

